

EU-HIP: EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform

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The general objective of EU-HIP (EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform) is to support the participating countries in enhancing their IT systems towards interoperability with HERA's platform, promoting data comparability and streamlining reporting across different systems.

For intelligence gathering and threat assessment, HERA needs support from the Member States and associated countries, and a comprehensive state-of-the-art IT system generating actionable insights for decision-making is crucial.

The upcoming HERA IT platform for intelligence gathering will only be operational if Member States have strong national IT systems that are interoperable with HERA's IT system and other relevant systems. EU-HIP supports participating countries to enhance and improve national IT systems in an efficient and coordinated manner, with the objective to obtain the needed interoperability with HERA's IT platform.

This will entail developing new IT systems and strengthening as well as aligning existing IT systems for the assessment of health threats and for intelligence gathering in the area of medical countermeasures at national level. Moreover, there is focus on promoting data comparability, and streamlining reporting to different systems. EU-HIP will facilitate integration of national IT systems with the HERA IT platform currently under development, and complement existing systems for early warning and response, epidemic intelligence, public health surveillance and medical countermeasures.

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